

Workplace Environment and Performance of State Universities in South East, Nigeria

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The study evaluated the Workplace Environment and Performance of State Universities in South East, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to: examine the relationship between team work and students' satisfaction and evaluate the relationship between leadership style and creation of opportunities of state universities in South East, Nigeria. The area of the study was the state universities in South East, Nigeria. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. The actual population was three thousand, two hundred and fifty staff (3250). The adequate sample size of Three hundred and forty-four (344) staff, the study used Freund and William's statistic formula as quoted by (Uzoagulu, 2011) at 5% margin of error. The population of the study was drawn from the staff of these organizations under study using a stratified sampling method. Three hundred and seventeen (317) staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. Data was presented and analyzed using Likert Scale and the hypotheses using Pearson correlation coefficient (r). The findings indicated: i. Team work had significance positive relationship with the student's satisfaction $r(95, n = 317), .498 < .788 = p. < 0.05$, and Leadership style had significance positive relationship with the creation of opportunities in Nigerian South East State Universities $r(95, n = 317), .526 < .729 = p. < 0.05$. The study concluded that Team work and Leadership style had significance positive relationship with the student's satisfaction and creation of opportunities of state universities in South East, Nigeria. The study recommended among others that the institutions' management should establish a supportive atmosphere for teamwork in order to promote collaborative problem-solving, which ultimately results in improved outcomes. This approach will fosters individual development, enhances job satisfaction, and diminishes stress levels.

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ABSTRACT

Keywords: Workplace Environment; Performance; Teamwork; Leadership Style

Introduction

The modern workplace is characterized by its dynamic, diverse nature and constant evolution. With a thriving economy and an abundance of job opportunities, workers now have a wide range of choices available to them. As a result, businesses find themselves relying on their employees to a greater extent than employees rely on the business (Smith, 2011). Every organization aspires to have highly skilled employees who are dedicated to achieving the organization's goals and deliver high-performance results. Within higher institutions, like any other community within society, there exist numerous interpersonal, academic, socio-economic, political, and crucially, employment relationships. It is a spectacular kind of workplace environments, a conglomeration of intellectuals and well-informed individuals who hail from different socio-cultural, ethnic and religious environments and meet in educational institutions to pursue different aims and objectives (Akinsanya and Oludeyi, 2013). The diverse nature of people's demographic and professional characteristics for example education, orientation, experience, culture, identity, sex, religion, skills etc. makes individuals to react differently to workplace and work environment stimuli. The essence of commitment of staff in the workplace is on the fact that highly committed employees perform better on the job and are less likely to exhibit such anomalous workplace behaviour as high absenteeism or presenteeism, voluntary turnover, apathy etc. (Oludeyi, 2015).

The environment in which employees work significantly influences their performance. The impact of the working environment on employee performance, whether positive or negative, has been widely discussed (Chandrasekar, 2011). The quality of a job is increasingly acknowledged as a crucial factor guiding policy decisions in the workplace. It is essential for countries worldwide to establish surveys on working conditions that incorporate comparable data on job quality. Workplace conditions surveys aim to capture the 'real' work activities that individuals carry out, rather than what is stated in their job description (Thirlon, Aleksynska, Berg and Johnston, 2019). Employee performance, which is a complex concept, refers to the degree of task accomplishment that constitutes their job performance. Similarly, Rizwan, Nazar, Nadeem & Abblas (2016) define employee performance in terms of work quantity, quality, and efficiency. It is also closely tied to productivity, which encompasses output quantity, output quality, output timeliness, job presence, work morale, work efficiency, and effectiveness. This is why Boorman and Motowidlo (2017) conceptualized employee performance as their effectiveness in performing tasks that contribute to the core aims of the organization, facilitated by a conducive operating environment. As rightly pointed out by Samson, et al. (2015), the importance of employee performance for the existence of an organization cannot be overstated. Undoubtedly, there are various factors that influence employee performance, with workplace influence being a prominent factor, as noted by Mathew and Khan (2015) who define employee performance as the combination of achievement, ability, and task perception.

Employees are the backbone of any organization. Among all the assets of any organization, employees are considered the most precious and significant (Ganesh, 2015). The structuring of the work environment can have a profound impact on influencing employees to perform at their best. Committed and highly motivated employees, who are provided with a conducive work environment, dedicate their time and energy towards achieving organizational goals. These individuals are increasingly recognized as the primary asset for any organization, as they contribute valuable intellectual capital, which has become crucial for many organizations (Renne, 2015). These factors were the basis for conducting a study on the workplace environment and performance of State University in South East, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Workplace environment is one of the comprehensive concepts of physical, psychological and social working conditions which institutions. Consciously cultivating the work environment entails various measures aimed at enhancing quality of life, increasing satisfaction derived from work, fostering opportunities for personal growth, establishing safe and healthy workplaces, and promoting the creative and critical utilization of work system initiatives, all of which contribute to the effectiveness of workers. Study environment include the physical, psychological and social circumstances that affect the wellbeing as a student and experience of the studies. Work environments are the forces that are currently and continually influencing performance, motivation and employment relationship.

The institution immediate work environment in relation to physical layout and design of an office is extremely essential when it comes to maximizing individual performance. Lack of management support of employees, lack of team spirit, unsafe environment, Poor leadership style, unsuitable furniture, poor graduation rate, inappropriate lighting and university regulations adversely affect performance.

Therefore, inability of the institution to curtail the posing challenges could lead to poor student's satisfaction, poor creation of opportunities, lack of improved quality of teaching and quality in research, lack of duty competence, absenteeism/lack of punctuality and poor output of the institution. Based the background, the study evaluates the Workplace Environment and performance of Nigeria's South Eastern State Universities.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to evaluate the Workplace Environment and Performance of State Universities in South East, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to:

- i. Examine the relationship between team work and students satisfaction of state universities in South East, Nigeria.
- ii. Evaluate the relationship between leadership style and creation of opportunities of state universities in South East, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

- i. What is the relationship between team work and students satisfaction of state universities in South East, Nigeria?
- ii. What is the relationship between leadership style and creation of opportunities of state universities in South East, Nigeria?

Statement of Hypotheses

The following alternate hypotheses guided the study

- i. Team work had relationship with the student's satisfaction of state universities in South East, Nigeria.
- ii. Leadership style had relationship with the creation of opportunities of state universities in South East, Nigeria.

Review of the Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Workplace

A workplace, also known as a place of employment, serves as a designated venue where individuals carry out tasks, jobs, and projects on behalf of their employer. The nature of workplaces varies across industries and institutions, encompassing both indoor and outdoor settings. Additionally, workplaces can be flexible, allowing individuals to work from different locations on different days. The advent of technology has brought about a new form of workplace known as the virtual workplace, enabling remote work opportunities. The workplace itself can encompass diverse settings, including natural outdoor environments, traditional office spaces, or remote locations while traveling (Indeed, 2023). The responsibility lies with the institution to ensure a work environment that is safe and conducive to productivity for its employees. The Department of Labor (DOL) offers guidance and regulations pertaining to various aspects of the workplace, such as workers' compensation, break and lunch requirements, leave policies, handling inclement weather and emergencies, equal employment opportunities, and unemployment compensation. (Liveaboutdotcom, 2023).

Environment

The environment provides a wide array of products and services necessary for sustaining life. Each resource holds its own level of importance and possesses significant value. Environmental resources encompass various materials, services, and elements that are beneficial to society and humans. They can be anything that fulfills the needs of everyday life. Examples of environmental resources include nourishment derived from living organisms and plants, fuel for cooking and transportation, wind energy, oil, and more. The environment plays a crucial role in supplying a diverse range of products and services vital for the continuation of life. Each resource has its own inherent importance and is highly valued (Vedantu, 2023).

Workplace Environment

The workplace environment is the intangible atmosphere that permeates the office and is experienced by all employees. It is a challenging aspect to define precisely, as it is not something tangible but rather linked to each individual employee's subjective perception. The workplace environment, or working atmosphere, is what cannot be seen or touched, yet it greatly influences employees' enjoyment of going to work, their comfort in entering the office, their willingness to dedicate time to their tasks, and even their likelihood of recommending the company to others (Rodríguez, 2021).

A work environment encompasses various elements that shape the setting in which employees carry out their work and significantly impact their experience. While some elements are evident, such as the physical environment including wall treatments or the presence of indoor plants, others are more subtle, such as company politics or the compatibility of a coworker's personality with the company culture. Both full-time and part-time professionals are profoundly influenced by their office environment since they perform their duties within it (Glassdoor, 2021).

A positive work environment has the power to uplift moods, enhance concentration, and foster a productive working approach for both employees and students.

Components of Workplace Environment that Formed Part of the Objectives of the Study

Team work

Teamwork refers to the collaborative effort of individuals within an organization who join forces to achieve a shared objective or set of goals. In the contemporary work environment, teamwork can occur both in-person and increasingly through online platforms. It is important to acknowledge that modern teams differ significantly from those of the past. Today's teams are characterized by greater diversity and dynamism, encompassing individuals with unique skill sets those present new challenges and opportunities. Consequently, every project that necessitates teamwork can also serve as a means for personal growth and professional development (Zimmer, 2019).

Teamwork occurs when individuals work together in pursuit of a common goal, which can be either professional or personal in nature. Whether it involves collaborating to move furniture up a flight of stairs, launching a work-related project, or engaging in a game of soccer, teamwork requires the collective effort of individuals pooling their skills and resources (Shonna, 2022).

Leadership style

A leadership style encompasses the methods, characteristics, and behaviors that a leader employs when directing, motivating, and managing their teams. It is influenced by various factors, including the leader's personality, values, skills, and experiences, and significantly impacts the effectiveness of their leadership. Moreover, a leader's style shapes their approach to developing strategies, implementing plans, responding to changes, managing stakeholder expectations, and ensuring the well-being of their team (IMD, 2023).

Leadership is the capacity of individuals to inspire, influence, and guide others toward a shared goal or vision that benefits the entire organization. It encompasses several crucial functions, such as providing direction, delegating tasks, making decisions, setting goals, and fostering a positive work environment. In the dynamic and ever-changing business landscape of today, leaders are required to assume multiple roles, extending their influence beyond their

formal positions of authority. They serve as the backbone of organizations and possess the ability to shape the success of their teams (Emeritus, 2022).

Performance

Performance can be defined as the successful accomplishment of a specific task, measured against predetermined standards of accuracy, completeness, cost, and speed. Within the context of a contract, performance refers to the fulfillment of obligations in a manner that releases the performer from any liabilities stipulated in the agreement (McNamara, 2018).

It involves the successful completion of tasks through the application of knowledge, skills, and abilities. Performance is the result of various activities undertaken by an organization, serving as an indication of how tangible and intangible resources are invested to achieve desired goals (McNamara, 2018).

Components of Performance that Formed Part of the Objectives of the Study

Student's Satisfaction

The quality of the teaching staff is a crucial determinant of student satisfaction. Consequently, the utilization of student rating scales as an evaluative component in the teaching system has become more prevalent. Initially, universities implemented satisfaction surveys with two main objectives: to enable administrators to monitor teaching quality and to assist teaching staff in enhancing their teaching methods. However, present-day university student satisfaction surveys serve a broader range of purposes (Kulik, 2001). They are now utilized to evaluate the quality and accessibility of library resources, assess the adequacy of IT assistance and support for students, and gather student opinions on various social aspects of university life, among other uses (Wiki, 2023).

Creation of opportunities

Opportunity creation involves identifying present problems and finding ways to leverage them for future solutions. While not everyone in business possesses an entrepreneurial mindset, entrepreneurs play a crucial role in driving innovation and progress. They are often characterized as risk-takers, a quality that not everyone in the business world may possess. Nevertheless, entrepreneurs are indispensable because they act as catalysts for change, and sometimes change is necessary for advancement. The ability to create opportunities is an integral aspect of an entrepreneur's DNA.

Understanding the process of opportunity creation can help identify individuals within your team who possess the necessary creativity to explore uncharted territories and propel your business into new realms. By recognizing these individuals, you can strategically organize your workforce, providing them with the space and resources to nurture their innovative ideas. This fosters an environment where their creativity can thrive, leading to unique solutions and growth opportunities for your business (SixSigma, 2022).

Conceptual Framework of the study

Fig 2.1 Conceptual framework of the study

Theoretical Framework

The following theories guided the study: Goal-Setting Theory by Edwin Locke in the year 1968 and Human Relations Theory by Professor Elton Mayo in early 1920's; The study was based on the goal-setting theory, which emphasizes the importance of allocating time and energy to various factors such as providing performance incentives, managing processes, offering sufficient resources, and conducting workplace training.

Goal-Setting Theory

The goal-setting theory had been proposed by Edwin Locke in the year 1968. This theory suggests that the individual goals established by an employee play an important role in motivating him for superior performance. The required skills encompass the ability to engage employees in mutual goal setting, clarify role expectations, and provide regular performance feedback. Additionally, allocating time and energy to aspects such as providing relevant performance incentives, managing processes, ensuring adequate resources, and delivering workplace training is crucial. Furthermore, to drive the organization towards peak performance, managers and supervisors must prioritize the human aspect of their organization. This principle emphasizes human-to-human interaction, including offering individualized support and encouragement to each employee (Salaman & John, 2005).

Employee performance is a significant multidimensional construct that aims to achieve desired outcomes and is closely tied to the planned goals of an organization (Abbas and Yaqoob, 2009). Performance serves as a key factor in attaining organizational objectives and is intricately linked to planned outcomes (Sabir, Iqbal, Rehman, Shah, and Yameen, 2012). In this theory, employees' goal achievement is facilitated by creating an attractive, comfortable, satisfactory, and motivating work environment that instills a sense of pride and purpose in their work. The design and atmosphere of the working environment not only impact how individuals feel but also influence their work performance, commitment to the organization, and the generation of new knowledge within the organization (Taiwo, 2009).

Empirical Review

Team work and students satisfaction of state universities in South East, Nigeria. .

Enwezor and Emenike (2021) conducted a study examining the correlation between academic staff work environment, work orientation, and job satisfaction in Colleges of Education in South East, Nigeria. The study aimed to address three research questions and test three hypotheses at a significance level of 0.05. A correlation research design was employed for the study, and the population consisted of all 2,819 academic staff members across the Colleges of Education in the South East region of Nigeria. The sample size for the study included 800 academic staff members from the Colleges of Education, selected using a proportionate stratified sampling technique. Data collection was carried out using three sets of instruments: the "Questionnaire on Work Environment (QWE)," the "Questionnaire on Work Orientation (QWO)," and the "Minnesota Questionnaire on Job Satisfaction (QJS)." These instruments were validated by three experts from the Faculty of Education at Nnamdi Azikiwe University. Reliability analysis was conducted using Cronbach's alpha, yielding coefficients of 0.91 and 0.88 for the QWE and QWO instruments, respectively. To address research questions 1 and 2 and test hypotheses 1 and 2, Pearson Product Moment Correlation and t-test of correlation were used, respectively. Multiple regression analysis was employed to answer research question 3 and test hypothesis 3. The study's findings revealed a significant positive relationship between academic staff work environment and job satisfaction in Colleges of Education in the South East region of Nigeria, among other findings.

Okolocha, Akam, and Uchehara (2021) conducted a study investigating the impact of job satisfaction on job performance among university lecturers in the South-East region of Nigeria. While previous research has made strides in understanding the relationship between job satisfaction and employee performance, much of this research has been focused on foreign countries and non-academic staff. Therefore, this study aimed to examine the effect of job satisfaction on the job performance of university lecturers specifically in the South-East region of Nigeria. The study specifically examined the significant influence of responsibility and career advancement on the job performance of academic staff in public universities in this region. The research questions and hypotheses were

formulated in alignment with the study objectives. The survey research design was employed, and a sample size of 1,780 academic staff members was derived from a population of 9,269 academic staff in public universities in the South-East states of Nigeria. Questionnaires were distributed among academic staff members in the public universities of the South-East states of Nigeria, and the data collected were analyzed using a five-point Likert scale. Regression analysis and Pearson coefficient correlation were conducted to test the formulated hypotheses using SPSS version 20.0. Based on the data analysis, the study found that responsibility and career advancement have a positive and significant impact on the job performance of academic staff in public universities in the South-East region of Nigeria.

Ifechi, Okoli, and Nwosu (2022) conducted a study examining the influence of professional career development and teamwork on job satisfaction among lecturers in selected private universities in Nigeria. The objective of this study was to investigate the relationship between professional career development, teamwork, and job satisfaction, with the theoretical framework based on social exchange theory. The study utilized a descriptive survey research design to establish the linkages between these constructs. A structured questionnaire was distributed to 428 respondents from six selected private universities in Nigeria. The reliability of the measurement instrument was assessed using Cronbach's alpha. Correlation analysis was used to test hypothesis one, while regression analysis was employed to test hypotheses two, three, and four. The analysis revealed a statistically significant influence between professional career development, teamwork, and job satisfaction among lecturers in private universities in Nigeria. The findings of the study concluded that professional career development and teamwork have varying degrees of influence on job satisfaction among private university lecturers. Notably, teamwork exerted a greater level of influence on lecturers' job satisfaction compared to professional career development.

Adani, Kanayo and Okoli (2022) conducted a study on the Influence of Professional Career Development and Teamwork on Employee Job Satisfaction: Evidence from Private Universities in Nigeria. The purpose of this study was to examine the influence of professional career development and teamwork on job satisfaction among lecturers in selected private universities in Nigeria. Social exchange theory was used to establish the theoretical framework of this study. The study adopted descriptive survey research design to establish the relationship between professional career development, teamwork and job satisfaction. Structured questionnaire was distributed to 428 respondents in six selected private universities in Nigeria. The reliability of the measuring instrument was tested using Cronbach Alpha. Hypothesis one was tested using correlation analysis and regression analysis were employed for testing of hypotheses two, three and four. The result of the analysis showed that there is a statistical influence between the three constructs professional career development, teamwork and job satisfaction of private university lecturers in Nigeria. The research concludes that professional career development and teamwork exert different levels of influence on private university lecturers' job satisfaction and that teamwork exerts greater level of influence on lecturers' job satisfaction.

Leadership style and creation of opportunities of state universities in South East, Nigeria.

Dzakpasu, Amankwah, Konin and Barbanas (2022) carried out a study on the Leadership styles of head teachers' and job satisfaction perceived by Ghanaian public basic school teachers. In a school setting, apart from teaching and learning, school leadership is seen as one of the critical ingredients for successful schools. Based on this proposition, the study sought to examine the relationship between head teachers' leadership styles and job satisfaction as perceived by public basic school teachers in Kwabre East Municipal, Ghana. Specifically, the study was conducted to determine the predominant head teachers' leadership style used as perceived by the teachers, determine the level of teachers' job satisfaction, and ascertain the relationship between leadership styles of head teachers and teachers' job satisfaction. The study adopted a descriptive survey design, and 286 teachers were randomly selected for the study. A questionnaire was the main data collection instrument for the study. The collected data were analyzed using means, standard deviations and Spearman Correlation Moment Product. Results indicated that head teachers predominantly used a transformational leadership style, and teachers generally had a moderate level of job satisfaction.

Shahbal, Khan and Al-Kubaisi (2022) conducted a study on the Leadership Styles, Role, and Opportunities; Reflection in Educational Management System. Leadership is the key factor in organizing managing and uplifting an organization. The implications of this concept extend to various aspects of life, particularly within the educational

realm, where the need for standardized, effective, and advanced knowledge is essential to meet societal demands on an international, national, and scientific level. Consequently, educational management plays a crucial role in aligning leadership styles, creating opportunities, and defining roles within the educational system. To gather relevant information on the topic, data was thoroughly examined using search engines such as Google Chrome, Firefox, and Microsoft Edge. Various databases were explored, including Google Scholar, Cochrane Collaboration, Emerald insight, MEDLINE, CINAHL, EMBASE, Taylor & Francis, Science Direct, Scopus, PubMed, and JSTOR. The research employed specific keywords such as "Leadership Styles," "Roles," and "Opportunities in the Educational Management System," using syntaxes such as "and," "or," "with," "if," etc. The aim of educational management is to enhance and stabilize educational outcomes by promoting factors that contribute to their improvement.

Adetola, Yemisi, and Soyemi (2022) conducted a study examining the relationship between leadership styles and the innovativeness of librarians in universities located in South-West Nigeria. Innovativeness is a highly valued trait among employees as it can contribute to improved organizational performance. Therefore, the study aimed to investigate how different leadership styles influence the innovativeness of librarians in the aforementioned universities. The research design adopted for the study was a survey research design. The population of interest consisted of 861 librarians working in universities within the South-West region of Nigeria. A sample size of 273 respondents was determined using the Taro Yamane formula, and a multistage sampling technique was employed to select the participants. Data collection was carried out using a validated and structured questionnaire. The reliability of the variables was assessed using Cronbach's alpha, which yielded coefficients ranging from 0.82 to 0.95. A high return rate of 99.2% was achieved for the completed questionnaires. Descriptive and inferential statistics, including linear regression and multiple regression analysis, were employed to analyze the collected data. The findings revealed that leadership styles had a significant influence on the innovativeness of librarians, as indicated by the significant R² value of 0.034, t-value of 2.943, β -value of 0.185, and p-value of less than 0.05.

Abdulkarim (2022) conducted a study investigating the relationship between leadership styles of Business Education administrators and staff job performance in Federal Colleges of Education (Technical) in the South-South region of Nigeria. The study had five specific objectives, five research questions, and two hypotheses as guiding factors. A descriptive-correlation research design was adopted to describe the variables and establish their relationship. The population and sample for the study consisted of 131 respondents, including 12 administrators and 119 staff members from the Business Education program in Federal Colleges of Education (Technical) located in Asaba and Omoku, Nigeria, during the 2021/2022 academic session. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire that underwent face validation. The reliability of the instrument was assessed using Cronbach's alpha, which yielded reliability indexes of 0.72 and 0.76 for the two clusters of the questionnaire, with an average of 0.74. To address research questions 1, 2, and 4, mean and standard deviation were utilized, while Spearman Rank Correlation (r) was employed for research questions 3 and 5, as well as the null hypotheses. Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 21.0 was used for all data analysis. The relationship scales were interpreted using the scales by Bryman and Bell (2011). The results of the study indicated that Business Education administrators predominantly utilized democratic/transformational leadership styles to drive job performance. Additionally, the findings revealed a moderate positive and significant relationship between the leadership styles of Business Education administrators and staff job performance, which was deemed satisfactory.

Aransi (2022) conducted a study examining the influence of principal leadership styles and teachers' work-related flow experience on teachers' productivity in Osun State, Nigeria. The study aimed to assess the impact of these factors on teachers' effectiveness in both academic and non-academic activities. The research employed a descriptive survey research design and utilized both probability and non-probability sampling techniques to select a total of 200 respondents. To gather information, validated quantitative instruments were utilized, namely the 'Work-Related Flow Questionnaire' (WRFQ), 'Leadership Styles Questionnaire' (LSQ), and 'Teachers' Productivity Questionnaire' (TPQ). These instruments demonstrated reasonable reliability coefficients and were administered to the participants. Regression analysis was employed to address the three objectives of the study and answer the research questions. The empirical findings revealed that principal leadership styles, specifically transformational, laissez-faire, and transactional leadership styles, had both negative and positive influences on teachers' productivity, as indicated by the t-values (-0.480, -2.710, and 0.633) respectively with a sample size of 273. Furthermore, teachers' work-related flow experience demonstrated a positive and significant effect on teachers' productivity, with a t-value of 3.18 and p-value of 0.002, which was less than the significance level of 0.05. The combined influence of teachers'

work-related flow experience and principal leadership styles accounted for 55.8% of the variation observed in teachers' productivity. Based on these findings, the study concluded that principal leadership styles and teachers' work-related flow experience play crucial roles in determining teachers' effectiveness in both academic and non-academic activities.

Gap in Knowledge

Some studies done were carried outside Workplace environment and performance of state universities in South East, Nigeria and did not focus to best of my knowledge on the team work and students satisfaction, leadership style and creation of opportunities, graduation rate and improved quality and university regulations and quality in research of state universities in South East, Nigeria. Most of the studies reviewed analysed their data through Proportionate stratified random sampling procedure, Purposive random sampling method, Linear regression and Pearson correlation, Pearson Product Moment Correlation, Regression analysis and Pearson coefficient correlation, Simple linear regression, Proportionate stratified random sampling technique, Pearson's product-moment correlation and linear regression using the Software Package for Service Solution (SPSS) tested, Stratified random sampling technique, Correlation analysis and regression analysis, Means, standard deviations and Spearman Correlation Moment Product, Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 21.0 and Survey research design. respectively while the present study made use of Z test to test the hypotheses. Therefore, the study aimed at filling this research gap by evaluating the workplace environment and performance of state universities in South East, Nigeria.

Methodology

The area of the study was five (5) State Universities in South East, Nigeria. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. The actual population was three thousand, two hundred and fifty staff (3250). the adequate sample size of Three hundred and forty four (344) staff, the study used Freund and William's statistic formula as quoted by (Uzoagulu 2011) at 5% margin of error. The population of the study was drawn from the staff of these organizations under study using a stratified sampling method. Three hundred and seventeen (317) staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. That gave 92percent response rate. The validity of the instrument was tested using content analysis and the result was good. The reliability was tested using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r). It gave a reliability co-efficient of 0.780 which was also good. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were analyzed using Pearson correlation coefficient (r) statistic tool.

Data Presentation and Analyses

The Relationship between team work and students satisfaction of state universities in South East, Nigeria.

Table 1: Responses on the relationship between team work and students satisfaction of state universities in South East, Nigeria.

		5	4	3	2	1	ΣFX	-	SD	Decision
		SA	A	N	DA	SD		X		
1	Achieving an understanding of new idea the students acquires help the lecturers or peers.	675 135 42.6	384 96 30.3	48 16 5.0	58 29 9.1	41 41 12.9	1206 317 100%	3.80	1.405	Agree
2	The students work together in small groups to pursue common goals.	560 112 35.3	384 96 30.3	75 25 7.9	36 18 5.7	66 66 20.8	1121 317 100%	3.54	1.525	Agree
3	There is integration of new information and knowledge networks into the learning community.	530 106 33.4	500 125 39.4	78 26 8.2	40 20 6.3	40 40 12.6	1188 317 100%	3.75	1.321	Agree
4	Teamwork improves student's performance regarding higher-order thinking activities.	600 120 37.9	468 117 36.9	21 7 2.2	84 42 13.2	31 31 9.8	1204 317 100%	3.80	1.333	Agree
5	The lecturer facilitates group work and ensures students have a positive group work experience.	525 114 36.0	364 117 36.9	54 18 5.7	40 20 6.3	48 48 15.1	1031 317 100%	3.72	1.400	Agree
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.722	1.3968	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 1, 231 respondents out of 317 representing 72.9 percent agreed that achieving an understanding of new idea the students acquires help the lecturers or peers with mean score 3.80 and standard deviation of 1.405. The students work together in small groups to pursue common goals 208 respondents representing 65.6 percent agreed with mean score of 3.54 and standard deviation of 1.525. There is integration of new information and knowledge networks into the learning community 237 respondents representing 69.8 percent agreed with mean score of 3.75 and standard deviation of 1.321. Teamwork improves student's performance regarding higher-order thinking activities 237 respondents representing 74.8 percent agreed with mean score of 3.80 and 1.333. The lecturer facilitates group work and ensures students have a positive group work experience 231 respondents representing 72.9 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.72 and standard deviation 1.400

The relationship between leadership style and creation of opportunities of state universities in South East, Nigeria

Table 2: Responses on the relationship between leadership style and creation of opportunities of state universities in South East, Nigeria

		5 SA	4 A	3 N	2 DA	1 SD	ΣFX	- X	SD	Decision
1	The transformational leader gain trust and confidence of the students to achieve results.	515 103 32.5	592 148 46.7	21 7 2.2	22 44 13.9	15 15 4.7	1165 317 100%	3.88	1.148	Agree
2	The charismatic leadership of the lecturers encourage and show students towards new ideas in the University.	420 84 26.5	592 148 46.7	3 1 .3	76 38 12.0	46 46 14.5	1137 317 100%	3.59	1.374	Agree
3	the lecturers leads students toward meeting their goals through entrepreneurial leadership skills	460 92 29.0	600 150 47.3	18 6 1.9	80 40 12.6	29 29 9.1	1187 317 100%	3.64	1.459	Agree
4	Lecturers are innovative and so they apply innovation and creativity to manage the students and projects.	540 108 34.1	590 118 37.2	69 23 7.3	12 6 1.9	62 62 19.6	1273 317 100%	3.85	1.338	Agree
5	Lecturer students participative qualities encourage new initiatives.	675 135 42.6	388 97 30.6	42 14 4.4	86 43 13.6	28 28 8.8	1219 317 100%	3.56	1.476	Agree
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.704	1.359	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 2, 251 respondents out of 317 representing 79.2 percent agreed that the transformational leader gain trust and confidence of the students to achieve results with mean score 3.88 and standard deviation of 1.148. The charismatic leadership of the lecturers encourage and show students towards new ideas in the University 232 respondents representing 73.2 percent agreed with mean score of 3.59 and standard deviation of 1.374. The lecturers lead students toward meeting their goals through entrepreneurial leadership skills 242 respondents representing 76.3 percent agreed with mean score of 3.64 and standard deviation of 1.459. Lecturers are innovative and so they apply innovation and creativity to manage the students and projects 226 respondents representing 71.3 percent agreed with mean score of 3.85 and 1.338. Lecturer students participative qualities encourage new initiatives 232 respondents representing 73.2 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.56 and standard deviation 1.476

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One: Team work had relationship with the student’s satisfaction of state universities in South East, Nigeria

Table 3: Correlations for Hypothesis 1

		Achieving an understanding of new idea the students acquires help the lecturers or peers.	The students work together in small groups to pursue common goals.	There is integration of new information and knowledge networks into the learning community.	Teamwork improve students performance regarding higher-order thinking activities.	The lecturer facilitates group work and ensures students have a positive group work experience.
Achieving an understanding of new idea the students acquires help the lecturers or peers.	Pearson Correlation	1	.714**	.684**	.603**	.621**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	317	317	317	317	317
The students work together in small groups to pursue a common goals.	Pearson Correlation	.714**	1	.611**	.499**	.498**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	317	317	317	317	317
There is integration of new information and knowledge networks into the learning community.	Pearson Correlation	.684**	.611**	1	.611**	.788**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	317	317	317	317	317
Teamwork improve students performance regarding higher-order thinking activities.	Pearson Correlation	.603**	.499**	.611**	1	.675**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	317	317	317	317	317
The lecturer facilitates group work and ensures students have a positive group work experience.	Pearson Correlation	.621**	.498**	.788**	.675**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	317	317	317	317	317

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 3 showed the Pearson correlation matrix on Team work and student’s satisfaction showing the correlation coefficients, significant values and the number of cases. The correlation coefficient shows .498 <.788. This value indicates that correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2 tailed) and implies that Team work had significant positive relationship with the student’s satisfaction of state universities in South East, Nigeria (r= .498 <.788). The computed correlations coefficient is greater than the table value of r = .000 with at alpha level for a two-tailed test (r= .498 <.788,p <.05).

Decision Rule

The decision rule is to accept the null hypothesis if the computed r is less than the tabulated r otherwise reject the null hypothesis.

Decision

Since the computed ($r = .498 < .788$) was greater than the table value of .000, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we concluded that team work had significant positive relationship with the student’s satisfaction of state universities in South East, Nigeria as reported in the probability value of ($r = .498 < .788., p < .05$).

Hypothesis Two: Leadership style had relationship with the creation of opportunities of state universities in South East, Nigeria

Table 4: Correlations for Hypothesis 2

		The transformational leader gain trust and confidence of the students to achieve results.	The charismatic leadership of the lecturers encourage and show students towards new ideas in the University.	the lecturers leads students toward meeting their goals through entrepreneurial leadership skills	Lecturers are innovative and so they apply innovation and creativity to manage the students and projects.	Lecturer students participative qualities encourage new initiatives.
The transformational leader gain trust and confidence of the students to achieve results.	Pearson Correlation	1	.729**	.730**	.589**	.592**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	317	317	317	317	317
The charismatic leadership of the lecturers encourage and show students towards new ideas in the University.	Pearson Correlation	.729**	1	.747**	.606**	.607**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	317	317	317	317	317
the lecturers leads students toward meeting their goals through entrepreneurial leadership skills	Pearson Correlation	.730**	.747**	1	.601**	.581**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	317	317	317	317	317
Lecturers are innovative and so they apply innovation and creativity to manage the students and projects.	Pearson Correlation	.589**	.606**	.601**	1	.526**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	317	317	317	317	317
Lecturer students participative qualities encourage new initiatives.	Pearson Correlation	.592**	.607**	.581**	.526**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	317	317	317	317	317

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4 showed the Pearson correlation matrix on leadership style and creation of opportunities of state universities in South East, Nigeria. showing the correlation coefficients, significant values and the number of cases. The correlation coefficient shows $.526 < .729$. This value indicates that correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2 tailed) and implies that leadership style had significant positive relationship with the creation of opportunities of state universities in South East, Nigeria. ($r = .484 < .782$). The computed correlations coefficient is greater than the table value of $r = .000$ with at alpha level for a two-tailed test ($r = .526 < .729, p < .05$).

Decision Rule

The decision rule is to accept the null hypothesis if the computed r is less than the tabulated r otherwise reject the null hypothesis.

Decision

Since the computed ($r = .526 < .729$) is greater than the table value of $.000$, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we concluded that leadership style had significant positive relationship with the creation of opportunities of state universities in South East, Nigeria. as reported in the probability value of ($r = .526 < .729, p < .05$).

Discussion of Findings

The Relationship between Team Work and Students Satisfaction

From the result of the hypothesis one, the computed ($r = .498 < .788$) was greater than the table value of $.000$, we concluded that team work had significant positive relationship with the student's satisfaction of state universities in South East, Nigeria as reported in the probability value of ($r = .498 < .788, p < .05$). In the support of the result in the literature review, Enwezor and Emenike (2021) conducted a study examining the correlation between the academic staff work environment, work orientation, and job satisfaction in Colleges of Education located in the South East region of Nigeria. The findings of the study revealed a significant and positive relationship between the academic staff work environment and their job satisfaction in the colleges of education in the South East, Nigeria. Okolocha, Akam, and Uchehara (2021) conducted a study on the Effect of Job Satisfaction on Job Performance of University Lecturers in South-East, Nigeria. Based on the data analyzed, the following findings were summarized that responsibility, career advancement, has positive significant effect on the job performance of the academic staff of public universities in South East, Nigeria. Adani, Kanayo and Okoli (2022) conducted a study on the Influence of Professional Career Development and Teamwork on Employee Job Satisfaction: Evidence from Private Universities in Nigeria. The result of the analysis showed that there is a statistical influence between the three constructs professional career development, teamwork and job satisfaction of private university lecturers in Nigeria. The research concludes that professional career development and teamwork exert different levels of influence on private university lecturers' job satisfaction and that teamwork exerts greater level of influence on lecturers' job satisfaction.

The Relationship between Leadership Style and Creation of Opportunities

From the result of the hypothesis two, the computed ($r = .526 < .729$) was greater than the table value of $.000$, we concluded that leadership style had significant positive relationship with the creation of opportunities of state universities in South East, Nigeria as reported in the probability value of ($r = .526 < .729, p < .05$). In the support of the result in the literature review, Adetola, Yemisi and Soyemi (2022) conducted a study on the Leadership Styles and Innovativeness of Librarians in Universities in South-West, Nigeria. The findings revealed that leadership styles ($R^2 = 0.034, t = 2.943, \beta = .185, p < 0.05$) had a significant influence on librarians' innovativeness. Abdulkarim (2022) conducted a study on Business Education Administrators' Leadership Style and Staff Job Performance in Federal Colleges of Education (Technical) in South-South, Nigeria. The results of the study revealed that Business Education administrators used democratic/transformational leadership styles to drive job performance. The results also showed moderate positive and significant relationship between leadership styles of Business Education administrators and staff job performance which was deemed satisfactorily.

Summary of the Findings

- i. Team work had significance positive relationship with the student's satisfaction of state universities in South East, Nigeria, $r(95, n = 317), .498 < .788 = p. < 0.05$
- ii. Leadership style had significance positive relationship with the creation of opportunities of state universities in South East, Nigeria, $r(95, n = 317), .526 < .729 = p. < 0.05$

Conclusion

The study concluded that Team work and Leadership style had significance positive relationship with the student's satisfaction and creation of opportunities of state universities in South East, Nigeria. Committed employees who are highly motivated in terms of conducive work environment contribute their time and energy to the pursuit of organizational goals and are increasingly acknowledged to be the primary asset available to an organization; they provide the intellectual capital that for many organizations has become their most critical asset.

Recommendations

In view of the findings, the following recommendations were proffered

1. The management of the institutions should create enabling environment for Team work to facilitate collaborative problem-solving which leads to better outcomes. This will encourage personal growth, increases job satisfaction, and reduces stress.
2. Leadership style is of great importance to any organization hence the institutions need to have the ability to know the most effective leadership style that is suitable for their organization or situation to succeed.

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